
Clinical symptoms, underlying pathogenesis, and the prospect of tailored therapies have all benefited from genetic discoveries in Parkinson's disease

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Abstract: Clinical symptoms, underlying pathogenesis, and the prospect of tailored therapies have all benefited from genetic discoveries in Parkinson's disease. Even as our understanding of disease biology improves, there are still knowledge gaps that must be filled in the future. Reliable biomarkers that uniquely recapitulate pathophysiological aspects are necessary for patient classification and medication response tracking. Genetic testing is essential in 'idiopathic' or 'sporadic' PD patients to identify those who would benefit from genotype-driven treatment. Genotype-dependent segmentation of research participants will broaden the possible usefulness of targeted treatments. Biomarker-assisted clinical trials will benefit tremendously from new adaptable designs. Recent breakthroughs in genotype-driven therapy, on the other hand, should deliver considerable benefits for Parkinson's patients in the medium term and lead to the development of the first disease-modifying drugs.

1. Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative condition defined by the buildup of specific-synuclein species in the nigrostriatal dopaminergic neurons and extranigral brain areas (Fujita et al. 2014; Moore et al. 2005; Schapira and Jenner 2011). The pathogenesis is complicated, including a number of molecular mechanisms. Despite substantial study into the molecular causes of Parkinson's disease, no disease-modifying medicines are now available, and routine patient management is primarily symptomatic. Despite the fact that monogenic causes of Parkinson's disease (mPD) account for a small percentage of cases, studying genetic variations sheds insight on individual disease causes and offers a unique potential for drug discovery and, ultimately, genotype-driven therapy (Blauwendraat et al. 2020). In idiopathic PD, biological discoveries and clinical features of mPD can be used to discover shared disease processes (IPD). Selected IPD patients may share molecular pathways with mPD, indicating that pathway-targeted treatments are needed (Redenek et al. 2017). The discovery of accurate biomarkers that allow individual IPD patients to be stratified according to their underlying disease and the development of appropriate clinical trial designs are required for the identification of such IPD patients. Furthermore, using genotyping to find individuals with mPD is a necessary step in gathering a large number of potential study participants for genotype-driven therapy choices and clinical trials. However, genetic testing of Parkinson's patients is not commonly used in clinical practice, and cooperative research activities will be required to achieve future recruitment objectives. Unlike mPD, IPD is a complex genetic illness in which the combination of genetic risk factors and environmental variables plays a key role in disease progression. Individual identification of risk variants can help researchers learn more about a disease's pathogenesis without having to rely on a monogenic feature. Polygenic risk score, blood-based biomarkers (e.g., assessing enzyme activity in peripheral tissue), and neuroimaging techniques have all been used or are currently being tested for classification of individuals with IPD (e.g., by studying brain energy metabolism).

Complex combinations between hereditary and environmental variables generate monogenic Parkinson's disease (PD). Autosomal dominant mPD is caused by mutations in SNCA (-synuclein), LRRK2 (Leucine Rich Repeat Kinase 2), and VPS35 (VPS35 Retromer Complex Component), whereas autosomal-recessive mPD is caused by mutations in PRKN (Parkin), PINK1 (PTEN-induced kinase 1), and PARK7 (oncogene DJ-1) (among others (Lill 2016). Although SNCA was the first PD-related gene discovered about 25 years ago, it is extremely rare, whereas LRRK2 mutations are the most common cause of mPD (Cookson 2015). The discovery of the autosomal-recessive genes PRKN, PINK1, and PARK7 connected mitochondrial failure to genetic reasons in the

genesis of Parkinson's disease (Exnre et al. 2012). Even though parkinsonism is only one of the presenting symptoms and just part of a more complicated or unusual phenotype (e.g., in DNAJC6 mutation carriers), monogenic causes are frequently included under the umbrella label of mPD (Puschmann 2013). Grünewald et al. (2013) and Klein et al. (2007) both questioned whether molecular insights into causal genes for atypical traits give translatable discoveries to IPD. Furthermore, numerous genes have not yet been replicated in separate families or groups. Furthermore, because most varieties are extremely uncommon, specialized treatments are unlikely to be discovered. Variants in the GBA (Glucosylceramidase Beta) gene are an unambiguous and common risk factor for the development of PD and a prospective potential treatment target, in addition to mPD, which follows Mendelian inheritance laws.

2. In monogenic Parkinson's disease, drug targets are important.

Most mPD genes and GBA converge on distinct molecular mechanisms, which can be divided into three categories: I-synuclein aggregation (Dehay et al. 2015), (ii) endosome-related involvement (Hafner et al. 2012; Dehay et al. 2013; Smolders and Van Broeckhoven 2020), and (iii) mitochondrial impairment (Smolders and Van Broeckhoven (Exnre et al. 2012). Brüggemann and Klein (2019) identified these pathways as prospective pharmacological targets for the disease-modifying therapy of mPD. Despite the fact that mPD has assisted in the identification of these target pathways for decades, genetic stratification in clinical trials has only just begun (Dehay et al. 2015; Shults et al. 2004).

The involvement of-synuclein aggregation and the SNCA gene in IPD-Synuclein aggregation is the pathophysiological hallmark of IPD, as evidenced by substantial post-mortem research (Moore et al. 2005; Kellie et al. 2014). As the principal cause of cell-to-cell propagation of-synuclein pathology in PD, mutations in the SNCA gene predispose to greater-synuclein accumulation and aggregation (Xu and Pu 2016). Point mutations affect the aggregative characteristics of-synuclein, whereas duplications or triplications result in enhanced production of the wildtype allele with a gene dosage effect (Book et al. 2018). -Synucleinopathy has been reported in people with IPD and SNCA mutations, as well as people with other types of mPD (Poulopoulos et al. 2012). In mPD, however, the histopathological alterations are more varied, with tau pathology in some LRRK2 carriers and the lack of-synucleinopathy in most PRKN mutation carriers (Henderson et al. 2019; Schneider and Alcalay 2017). The overall evidence of neuropathologic alterations in mPD is currently limited due to a scarcity of autopsied es.

The lysosomal or ubiquitin-proteasome systems (UPS) are unable to remove formed-synuclein oligomers, leading to the development of Lewy bodies (Volpicelli-Daley et al. 2016). Injection of-synuclein fibrils into the brain initiates long-term-synuclein aggregation and propagation in linked brain areas of model organisms (Luk et al. 2012; Dehay et al. 2016) and human individuals, according to rodent models (Luk et al. 2012; Dehay et al. 2016). (McCann et al. 2016). The Braak stages indicate the ascending transmission of-synuclein disease via brain structures, and they have significantly impacted our current understanding of PD pathogenesis (McCann et al. 2016). Different target mechanisms are currently being discussed to combat the progressive propagation of-synuclein pathology: I decreased-synuclein production, (ii) decreased intracellular-synuclein aggregation, (iii) enhanced intracellular-synuclein degradation, (iv) enhanced extracellular-synuclein degradation, and (v) blocking extracellular-synuclein uptake by neurons (Dehay et al. 2015). These target mechanisms may also apply to mPD forms with-synuclein disease, although they are not specific and do not interact with alterations in upstream genes or pathways.

By employing a variety of methods to reduce-synuclein expression in animal models, viral vectors successfully mediated the in-vivo production of siRNA (small-interfering RNA; double-stranded, non-coding RNA molecules that typically lead to the targeted degradation of complementary mRNA molecules) against SNCA in the substantia nigra (Volpicelli-Daley et al. 2016). β -2-adrenergic agonists (e.g., clenbuterol and salbutamol) and altering histone acetylation at the-synuclein gene promoter and enhancer regions might also be used to reduce-synuclein levels (Mittal et al. 2017). Intrabodies bind monomeric-synuclein and prevent it from oligomerizing (Bhatt et al. 2013). Thus, an increase in intracellular-synuclein aggregation as the cause of eventual nigral neurodegeneration in mice with viral vector-mediated-synuclein overexpression might be avoided (Volpicelli-Daley et al. 2016). In a mouse model, the chemical NPT200-11 (NPT200-11 trial, NCT02606682) was also able to inhibit the-synuclein interface with cell membranes and limit aggregation oligomerization (Bhatt et al. 2013). In preclinical settings, the phosphorylation of a rapamycin inhibitor promoted autophagy and reduced-synuclein disease (Boyd et al. 2013).

In mice, Nilotinib, a Tyrosine-protein kinase ABL1 inhibitor, inhibited protein aggregation, neurodegeneration, mitochondrial pyruvate carriers, and posttranslational alterations of-synuclein, with safety data currently available for human usage (PD Nilotinib, NCT02954978) (Pagan et al. 2016; Karuppagounder et al. 2014). Immunotherapy has been shown to reduce extracellular-synuclein or-synuclein aggregation in preclinical studies (Lindström et al. 2014; Tran et al. 2014; Spencer et al. 2017). PRX002, a humanized IgG1 monoclonal antibody that operates against epitopes of the-synuclein C-terminus, was the first-synuclein immunotherapy utilized in a clinical PD study (Brundin et al. 2017). An ascending-dose trial in healthy volunteers demonstrated the safety and acceptability of dosages up to 30 mg/kg, with a plasma half-life of 18.2 days that lasted two to four weeks following a single infusion (BP39529, NCT03100149) (Schenk et al. 2017).

In addition, optimized antibodies against distinct types of mono-, oligomeric, fibrils, and aggregated forms have been created in preclinical models to target distinct phases in-synuclein associated pathology (Wang et al. 2019). Furthermore, antisense oligonucleotides (ASOs; short-chain, synthetic, single-stranded oligonucleotides that bind to complementary mRNA and modify/hinder their respective translation) have been shown to be effective in in vitro, rodent, and primate models (Uehara et al. 2019; Alarcón-Ars et al. 2018; Choong and Mochizuki 2017).

3. The relevance of the GBA gene in lysosomal dysfunction in Parkinson's disease

The GBA gene produces the lysosomal hydrolase glucocerebrosidase (Ge), which transforms glucosylceramide to ceramide and glucose (Goker-Alpan et al. 2004; Neudorfer et al. 1996). Gaucher's disease is a lysosomal storage disorder caused by the buildup of undegraded substrates caused by compound heterozygous or homozygous GBA mutations (GD). Interestingly, parkinsonism is more common in GD patients, and heterozygous mutations in the GBA gene enhance the likelihood of developing PD (Goker-Alpan et al. 2004). As a result, heterozygous GBA mutations are the most frequent genetic risk factor for Parkinson's disease, with at least one putatively harmful mutation present in up to 10% of PD patients (Robak et al. 2017). The distinction between 'pathogenic' GBA variants (those that cause GD in a compound heterozygous/homozygous carrier state) and 'PD risk factor' GBA variants (those that show a correlation with PD risk but are not deemed causative for GD) is critical (Skrahina et al. 2020). The contrast between 'mild' and 'severe' variations (in individuals with type 1 or type 2/3 GD) is another categorization of GBA variations (Stirnemann et al. 2017). Carriers of moderate GBA variations (mGBA-PD) have a similar age at onset, phenotype, and disease course to IPD, but carriers of severe GBA variations (sGBA-PD) have a clearly elevated risk of dementia, with an earlier onset and faster cognitive deterioration (Davis et al. 2016). Carriers with modest mutations have a slower disease development than individuals with severe mutations, although it is still quicker than non-carriers (Cilia et al. 2016). In sGBA-PD and, to a lesser extent, in mGBA-PD, Ge activity is decreased, but IPD activity is only slightly decreased (Alcalay et al. 2015). Overall, an increase in Ge activity by targeted therapies may be beneficial only for a subset of IPD patients, as there is currently no convincing evidence for increased glycosylceramide accumulation in IPD patients (Niimi et al. 2020), and no efficacy and safety data on supraphysiological Ge levels are available. GBA deficiency, on the other hand, has been linked to-synuclein disease in a number of investigations, mostly preclinical. In a mouse model, decreased Ge activity generates higher amounts of ubiquitin/-synuclein aggregates, which is linked to motor and cognitive impairments (Sardi et al. 2013). A pathogenic feedback loop can explain the negative link between Ge activity and oligomeric-synuclein levels (Mazzulli et al. 2011). Changes in glycosphingolipid homeostasis can alter membrane composition and compromise lysosomal activity and vesicular transport, allowing-synuclein to aggregate more easily. Selective synaptic malfunction and neuronal degeneration arise from this mechanism (Schapira 2015).

In GBA-PD, but also in selected individuals with IPD, different therapy strategies are discussed: (i) substrate reduction (as is typically explored for the treatment of GD), (ii) exogenous Ge augmentation, and (iii) the increase of Ge activity (e.g., by amroxol). Substrate reduction can be accomplished by a variety of mechanisms: Glucosylceramide synthase inhibitors lower glycosphingolipid levels and are used to treat GD patients' hematological and visceral symptoms. The glucosylceramide synthase inhibitor venglustat adequately passed the blood-brain barrier (BBB) in humans, according to the clinical study GZ/SAR402671 (NCT02906020) (Davis et al. 2016). Venglustat reduced alpha-synuclein expression in mice models of GD-related synucleinopathy and alpha-synuclein overexpression (Mazzulli et al. 2011). A clinical phase II trial in patients is presently being conducted to see if this technique is also beneficial for GBA-PD (Moves PD, NCT02906020).

External Ge augmentation in the brain necessitates enzyme penetration across the blood-brain barrier, which is not possible with the enzymes utilized in GD therapy (Sun et al. 2020). A gene therapy-mediated viral overexpression of exogenous Ge in the brain, which has been demonstrated to cure behavioral and clinical problems by restoring the membrane glycosphingolipid equilibrium, is one strategy (Sardi et al. 2011;

Rockenstein et al. 2016). This finding lends credence to gene therapy aimed at raising Ge levels in the brain. In an SNCAA53T mice model, adeno-associated viruses (AAVs) are safe and physiologically active vectors that target Ge enhancement, reverse cognitive impairments, and decrease-synuclein (Hafner esen et al. 2012). Furthermore, a prior study found that by adjusting the delivery route, vector subtypes, small molecules, small molecular chaperones, and brain distribution in crucial brain areas, improved lysosomal Ge activity could be accomplished (Gegg and Schapira 2018). The third potential method for GBA-targeted therapeutics is to increase Ge activity, such as using the repurposed medication ambroxol, which has been found in nonhuman primates to increase Ge activity while lowering-synuclein and S129-phosphorylated—synuclein protein levels. Currently, the clinical studies UCL 15/0118 (NCT02941822) and R15-006 (NCT02914366) are evaluating the safety, effectiveness, and tolerance of ambroxol in people with Parkinson's disease (Migdalska-Richards et al. 2016, 2017). Preliminary human data is currently available, indicating that BBB crossing and molecular target site enrichment are adequate (Mullin et al. 2020). Noninhibitory Ge chaperones, such as NCGC758 and NCGC607, are another family of experimental drugs that can bind to Ge at the active site and cause conformational changes that boost Ge activity. These chaperones enter the brain, increasing lysosomal activity and Ge translocation to lysosomes while decreasing substrate and-synuclein accumulation (Dehay et al. 2013). Another clinical trial of afegostat tartrate in GD (AT2101, NCT00433147) demonstrated enhanced Ge activity and enzyme stability but no meaningful clinical benefit in GD patients (Boyd et al. 2013).

4. Clinical studies targeting LRRK2: challenges and opportunity

In a family with autosomal-dominant parkinsonism, the first gene mutation in LRRK2 was discovered (Paisán-Ruz et al. 2004). The LRRK2G2019S mutation is responsible for the great majority of LRRK2-associated PD cases globally, and it is particularly common in specific PD patient groups, such as Israel and North Africa (Trinh et al. 2018). Symptomatic LRRK2G2019S mutation carriers typically exhibit postural instability and gait difficulties (PIGD), but show very little cognitive and motor impairment throughout the course of the disease (Saunders-Pullman et al. 2018). The LRRK2G2019S results in a gain of function (GOF) with an increase in LRRK2 kinase activity when combined with other LRRK2 variations. The LRRK2 protein has a multidomain structure and belongs to the protein kinase family, which transfers phosphate groups to target proteins and plays a key role in the control and regulation of complicated cellular processes. LRRK2's kinase domain is comparable to that of mitogen-activated protein (MAP) kinases, which play a role in cellular stress mediation. Despite the fact that the exact mechanism of LRRK2 is unknown, the disease-causing GOF mutations allow for heuristic therapies that limit its function. Currently, there are two primary LRRK2-targeted therapeutic strategies: pharmacological suppression of LRRK2 activity and (ii) ASO-mediated gene silencing of the LRRK2 gene. Due to their intrathecal use, ASOs may escape possible peripheral side effects of kinase inhibitors, allowing them to lower LRRK2 activity in the CNS (Cookson 2015).

In a phase I research in healthy individuals, DNL201, a small molecule LRRK2 inhibitor, lowered LRRK2 activity by more than 90%. (DNLI-B-0001, NCT04551534). The treatment response (measured by a reduction in peripheral LRRK2 activity) in blood was measured by phosphorylation of the Ras-related protein Rab10 substrate and LRRK2 S935 phosphorylation. Healthy volunteers are currently being sought for a study with DNL151, a second LRRK2 inhibitor (DNLI-C-0001, NCT04557800) (Zeuner et al. 2019). Inhibition of LRRK2 in nonhuman primates was linked to lung morphological abnormalities in preclinical studies, raising possible safety concerns. The use of a high dosage of three drugs to target LRRK2 resulted in the accumulation of lamellar bodies in type-II pneumocytes (Fuji et al. 2015). However, after two weeks off the medication, these morphological abnormalities may be rectified, and no pulmonary problems were identified at the highest dosage. Furthermore, in human databases, there was no link between loss of function mutations and a putatively reduced LRRK2 kinase activity and a particular phenotypic or illness state (Whiffin et al. 2020).

5. PRKN and PINK1: Improving mitochondrial bioenergetics and antioxidative therapy options

One of the fundamental principles in the pathophysiology of Parkinson's disease is mitochondrial dysfunction. Mitochondria are essential for a variety of cellular operations, including energy supply, general cellular homeostasis, and neuronal survival. Environmental studies demonstrating the action of neurotoxic chemicals in blocking the mitochondria's electron transport chain (ETC) provided the first evidence for an involvement in PD (Schapira and Jenner 2011). The identification of the autosomal recessively inherited genes PRKN and PINK1 added to the evidence that mitochondrial malfunction plays a significant role in Parkinson's disease (Exnre et al. 2012). Under physiological settings, PINK1 attracts Parkin to damaged mitochondria, causing them to be cleared by the UPS, a process known as mitophagy (Park et al. 2018). As a result, Parkin and PINK1 work together as a molecular quality control system (McWilliams and Muqit 2017). In carriers of PRKN or PINK1 mutations,

possible therapeutic or preventative treatments include increasing PRKN or PINK1 expression, (ii) preventing Parkin or PINK1 inactivation, and (iii) controlling the downstream Parkin/PINK1 signaling pathway (Gaki and Papavassiliou 2014). Impaired mitochondrial biogenesis, fusion and fission processes, trafficking, metal ion and calcium homeostasis, neuroinflammation, and pro-apoptotic signaling are only a few of the pathogenic pathways associated with mitochondrial dysfunction (Dextera and Jenner 2013).

These many features might be used as therapy targets in the future. Improved clearance of dysfunctional mitochondria by mitophagy or other mitochondrial stress response pathways (Aman et al. 2020), mitochondrial biogenesis (e.g., by glucagon-like peptide 1 [GLP1] receptor agonist exenatide exposition) (Athauda et al. 2017), and gene therapies targeting (Cheng et al. 2020). Bioenergetic depletion and increased reactive oxygen species [ROS] production, on the other hand, are common to all types of mitochondrial dysfunction, and they most likely recapitulate one of the earliest pathophysiological events not only in mPD but also in IPD, and thus were the primary target mechanisms for most recent studies addressing mitochondrial pathology (Prasuhn et al. 2021).

Coenzyme Q10, a mitochondrial enhancer, has been the most thoroughly studied chemical, but it has failed to show benefit in most experiments. The lack of genetic classification of PD patients to enrich for patients with a substantial contribution of mitochondrial dysfunction might be one factor for the bad results (e.g., biallelic PRKN or PINK1 mutation carriers). Only two clinical studies (MitoPD [DRKS00015880] and PD-K2 [DRKS00019932]) that employ a combination of genetic classification and treatment-response monitoring by neuroimaging are currently recruiting (to our knowledge) (Prasuhn et al. 2019; Prasuhn et al. 2021). Homozygous/compound heterozygous PRKN/PINK1 mutation carriers, heterozygous PRKN/PINK1 mutation carriers, and two IPD groups characterized by statistical extrema as identified by a mitochondrial PRS are the groups studied in the MitoPD study (Prasuhn et al. 2019). IPD patients, homozygous/compound heterozygous PRKN/PINK1 mutation carriers, and healthy controls are all involved in the PD-K2 study (DRKS00019932). Both investigations will use multimodal neuroimaging as a surrogate marker to assess the favorable impacts of in-vivo brain energy metabolism, i.e., by measuring the change in energy equivalents utilizing 31Phosphorus Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy Imaging (31P-MRSI).

In monogenic PD, the interconnectivity of pathophysiological pathways: one treatment, multiple targets
The translation of molecular insights into the pathophysiology of IPD is one of the main motivations for studying mPD (Lin and Farrer 2014). The notion that molecular processes may be traced back to a single gene variation may be an oversimplification (Blauwendraat et al. 2020), as molecular processes are intertwined and complicated, as they are in mPD. -synuclein aggregation is the major illness mechanism in IPD, GBA-PD, and many but not all mPD es, according to our current understanding of PD pathogenesis. Tau pathology in LRRK2 and the lack of -synuclein accumulation in most autopsied PRKN mutation carriers are among the histopathological findings in mPD. As previously stated, -synuclein reduction is a primary goal of IPD. As a result, individuals with mPD who also have significant -synuclein pathology, particularly GBA-PD, should benefit from this pathophysiologically based treatment. The effect of these medicines on other types of mPD is less predictable. As a result, reliable biomarkers, such as -synuclein PET, are needed to adequately stratify PD patients, mostly irrespective of their genotype.

Ge enhancement reduces -synuclein pathology, making it a potential target for additional -synuclein-related types of mPD and the majority of IPD patients (Schapira 2015; Gan-Or et al. 2017). As a result, new glycosphingolipid biosynthesis inhibitors and noninhibitory pharmacological chaperones for glycosphingolipid processing enzymes are intriguing therapy options. Their clinical use is limited due to current limitations in terms of BBB penetration and off-target effects (Sybertz and Krainc 2014).

Third, there is evidence that practically all mPD-causing gene mutations are linked to a loss of mitochondrial function in some way (Shadrina et al. 2010). It's still up for dispute whether mitochondrial enhancers might help these patients. Fourth, data from epidemiological (Gao and Chen 2011), neuroimaging (Wilson et al. 2019a), post-mortem (McGeer et al. 1988), and preclinical (Lindestam Arlehamn et al. 2020) investigations suggests that neuroinflammation is a common pathophysiological feature of PD pathogenesis.

Although epidemiological research suggests that nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications may be beneficial, published meta-analyses have produced mixed outcomes (Bornebroek et al. 2007; Gagne and Power 2010; Samii et al. 2009).

Long-term usage of TNF-targeted antibodies reduces the risk of Parkinson's disease in individuals with inflammatory bowel illness (Peter et al. 2018). The interconnectedness of the proposed pathomechanisms of PD (-synuclein aggregation, endosome-related pathologies, and mitochondrial impairment) to neuroinflammation has been demonstrated for-synuclein pathology (Li et al. 2019), increased LRRK2 activity (Lee et al. 2017), Ge alterations (Sanyal et al. 2020), and PRKN/PINK1-related mitochondrial dysfunction. As a result, addressing neuroinflammation might give another important therapy option for Parkinson's disease. However, the exact cellular and humoral cause of neuroinflammation in Parkinson's disease is yet unknown, which limits the translation to therapeutic trials (Hirsch and Standaert 2020).

The continuing identification of disease processes may lead to a combination of individualized disease-modifying medicines for specific individuals with Parkinson's disease. This may be akin to the symptomatic treatment of Parkinson's disease patients, in which an optimal mix of anti-Parkinsonian medications is employed to address each patient's unique disease burden.

The role of targeted therapy in people with idiopathic Parkinson's disease

Too advanced neurodegeneration, inadequate target engagement, varied contributions of particular disease processes among IPD patients, and too short observation time are all potential causes of disease modifying failure in PD. Enriching study cohorts with genetically characterized individuals is critical for developing targeted medicines, and genotype-driven medicines are now being researched. Advances in genetic screening of Parkinson's disease patients have revealed that mPD and GBA-PD es are more common than previously thought (Skrahina et al. 2020). However, genetic testing is still not widely used in diagnostic procedures or clinical trial recruitment (Billingsley et al. 2018). This is becoming more important as a result of recent advances in translational medicines, which should not be denied to people who have an unknown but possibly treatment-qualifying genotype. To meet the diminishing window of opportunity for disease-modifying medicines, genetic testing should be explored early in the diagnostic care of PD patients. Consideration of genetic variations has already permeated clinical practice in other disciplines, such as cancer therapy, and has led to the creation of more efficient adaptive clinical trial designs (Li et al. 2007; Chow and Chang 2008; Berry 2012). For the therapeutic care of neurological patients, genetic testing will become increasingly relevant. For example, the new FDA-approved oligonucleotide medication Nusinersen necessitates genetic testing of individuals with spinal muscular atrophy in order to confirm the genetic diagnosis and determine eligibility for clinical trials (Chiriboga 2017). The creation of trial designs for neuroprotective therapies is difficult in and of itself: To demonstrate the disease-modifying effects of experimental medications, long interventional durations are required. It is desirable to select not yet afflicted patients for neuroprotective therapy while considering the long-term prodromal phase of PD (Heinzel et al. 2019). However, there is currently an information gap on a single person's conversion to PD.

Biomarkers are needed to categorize patients based on their underlying illness etiology in order to apply the current strategy of targeted therapy in mPD to IPD es (e.g., identifying those with critical mitochondrial impairment). Due to the lack of established and dynamic mechanism-based biomarkers, disease-modifying therapy for PD has become more difficult.

In the design of clinical trials for disease-modifying treatments, there is a need for trustworthy (para-) clinical biomarkers.

Biomarkers are primarily used in clinical PD studies to establish target engagement and measure disease progression. One important precondition for targeted therapy is the stratification of PD patients based on their primary illness processes (Redenek et al. 2017). The notions of state and trait biomarkers are crucial. State biomarkers frequently allude to a person's genetic origin. Monogenic gene variations (mPD) and the complex genetic architecture of IPD patients are also included (e.g., by PRS alluding to a major illness mechanism) (Heinzel et al. 2019). Trait biomarkers should be sensitive to treatments and should replicate the pathophysiological processes produced by the aforementioned genetic variations. Biomarkers based on peripheral tissues (e.g., blood or CSF based tests) and neuroimaging approaches are now being evaluated as dynamic biomarkers (Burciu et al. 2017; Postuma and Berg 2016; Bloem et al. 2019; Parnetti et al. 2019). There is one major worry concerning peripheral tissue biomarkers: Because the damaged brain areas have such a small biomass relative to the rest of the human body, hypersensitive analysis approaches are required, and they can still be swamped by physiological background noise (Davis et al. 2020). Peripheral biomarkers for the converging pathogenic pathways I-synuclein aggregation, (ii) endosome-related, and (iii) mitochondrial dysfunction have already been investigated, with mixed findings (Parnetti et al. 2019; Sharma et al. 2013). Their ability to treat reactions has not yet been assessed in most publications. Neuroimaging allows for mainly non-invasive

examinations of afflicted brain tissue. SNCA (Si et al. 2019), GBA (Greuel et al. 2020), LRRK2 (Simuni et al. 2020), and PRKN/PINK1 (Simuni et al. 2020) were the subjects of neuroimaging investigations (Van Nuenen et al. 2009; Anders et al. 2012; Nuenen et al. 2009) have been effectively employed to demonstrate variations in neuroanatomical and functional groups. Brain mapping of the serotonergic system in (pre-) symptomatic SNCAA53T mutant carriers (Wilson et al. 2019) or PET investigations of the serotonergic, dopaminergic, and cholinergic neurotransmitter systems in (pre-) symptomatic LRRK2 mutant carriers are examples of these investigations (Wile et al. 2017; Liu et al. 2018). Furthermore, recent research found that GBA or LRRK2 mutation carriers have a different network pattern in their brain metabolic networks (Schindlbeck et al. 2020). In conclusion, our findings imply that a variety of neuroimaging techniques may be used to depict genotype-specific brain alterations and may also be used to analyze pre-manifest mutant carriers. These neuroimaging biomarkers will create a unique window of opportunity for pre-manifest, targeted, and neuroprotective treatment methods, which are of great translational value. Despite these encouraging outcomes in genetically characterized Parkinson's disease individuals, the approaches utilized frequently lack specificity in terms of the possibly curable disease mechanism. As a result, imaging investigations are frequently confined to the investigation of neurodegenerative alterations and do not adequately account for disease biology. The study of brain energy metabolism for the diagnosis of mitochondrial malfunction is one prominent exception. The PET tracer [18F] BCPPEF, for example, has been used to evaluate Complex I dysfunction in Parkinson's disease patients (Wilson et al. 2020). Lactate (1H-MRSI) and high energy phosphates such as ATP levels may be measured in vivo using non-invasive magnetic resonance spectroscopic imaging (MRSI) (Bonvento et al. 2017). These approaches have also progressed to include dynamic measures (such as the rate of ATP production) (Clifford et al. 2020). Furthermore, a combination of functional MRI (measurement of the blood-oxygen-level-dependent signal, BOLD) and arterial spin labeling (ASL) can be used to investigate the cerebral oxygen consumption rate (Germuska et al. 2019), and near-infrared based spectroscopy can be used to quantify the redox state of Cytochrome c (Germuska et al. 2019). (Holper et al. 2019).

Different hardware setups and methodological restrictions limit the availability of these approaches. Before being used in clinical studies, intra-and intersite dependability must be assured and critically examined.

6. Conclusion

Clinical symptoms, underlying pathophysiology, and the possibility for targeted therapeutics have all benefited from genetic findings in Parkinson's disease (Brüggemann and Klein 2019). Even while our knowledge of disease biology is constantly improving, there are still information gaps that must be filled in the future. For patient categorization and therapy response tracking, reliable biomarkers that uniquely recapitulate pathophysiological characteristics are required. In 'idiopathic' or 'sporadic' PD patients, genetic testing is required to identify people who would benefit from genotype-driven therapy. The potential applicability of targeted medications will be expanded by genotype-dependent stratification of study participants. New adaptive designs will greatly enhance biomarker-assisted clinical trials. However, recent advances in genotype-driven treatments should, in the medium term, provide significant improvements for PD patients and lead to the creation of the first disease-modifying medications.

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